

A MODEL OF ORGANIZATIONAL EFFECTIVENESS OF THE TOP PROFITABLE BUSINESSES IN THAILAND

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Abstract

Economy is the key factor of creating national strength and global competitiveness whereas business organizations help develop national economy through employment and income generation to labor market. However, due to high competition, technological change that rapidly plays role in all sectors, trade liberalization and convenience of transportation, large business organizations increasingly import goods to compete with local ones. Consequently, the entrepreneurs must adapt in marketing, production and business management terms to retain professional skilled employees. This study aims to 1) examine the level of the following variables; spiritual leadership, organizational commitment, teamwork, job satisfaction and organizational effectiveness of the top profitable businesses in Thailand, 2) explore the influence of the variables; spiritual leadership, organizational commitment, teamwork and job satisfaction towards organizational effectiveness of the top profitable businesses in Thailand, and 3) develop a model of organizational effectiveness of the top profitable businesses in Thailand. The mixed research method was applied between the quantitative and qualitative ones. In view of the quantitative term, the sample group consisted of 320 informants who were employees working in the top profitable businesses in Thailand with the sample size calculated by 20-time criteria of the observed variables and proportional random sampling. Data collection was conducted through questionnaires that were later analyzed by the structural equation modelling. For the qualitative term, an in-depth interview was conducted with the major informants; employees working in the top profitable businesses in Thailand. The findings revealed that spiritual leadership, organizational commitment, teamwork, job satisfaction and organizational effectiveness of the top profitable businesses in Thailand were all at a high level, 2) spiritual leadership, organizational commitment, teamwork and job satisfaction influenced the organizational effectiveness of the top profitable businesses in Thailand at statistical significance level of .05, and 3) the organizational effectiveness model of the top profitable businesses in Thailand as developed by the researcher was called "LCST Model" (L = Spiritual Leadership, C = Organizational Commitment, S = Job Satisfaction, T = Teamwork). The qualitative findings also indicated that creating the organizational effectiveness of the top profitable businesses in Thailand, the management of such businesses needed to be flexible to cope with the change of the international economic environment and rapidly undertake continual and constant corporate communications including increasing cooperative efficiency of international business networks to promote successful creation of organizational effectiveness of the top profitable businesses in Thailand. The findings of this research can be also applied as a guideline for determination of policy for creating sustainable organizational effectiveness of the top profitable businesses in Thailand.

Keywords: Model/Organizational Effectiveness/Top Profitable Businesses/Thailand.

INTRODUCTION

The world situation is changing rapidly and becoming more serious. Under such circumstances, every country strengthens itself and creates potential for their own country in every aspect.

Especially, In Thailand the economic aspect is considered the key to making the country strong and able to compete with other countries. Facing the challenges that arise with business in the 21st century causes a phenomenon, called a wave of change. Many businesses in Thailand recognize that people are the most valuable asset that will allow a business to compete with external organizations (Bailey, Albassami & Meshal, 2016).

Business in Thailand is an organization that helps develop the country. It creates employment and distributes income from business entrepreneurs to the labor market. But due to the problems of high competition, rapid technological changes, free trade, convenience and speed of transportation, large businesses and products from abroad can compete more with domestic products. This creates difficulty, causing entrepreneurs to have to adjust in terms of marketing, production, and management with good governance. It is considered one of the problems of business entrepreneurs (Namjatturas, 2018). Business entrepreneurs, therefore, must innovate and promote innovation. Creating innovation means changing and improving existing models to create innovations. It is a key factor for businesses to create innovation and remain flexible for their survivals. Birchall and Tovstiga (2005: 4) state that the ability to innovate is very important. Capabilities that a business can create are knowledge and production in the past decade to become an important source of innovation. Moreover, innovation depends on the evolution of knowledge.

Top 100 successful businesses in Thailand in 2014-2018 considering from the highest income for the fiscal years 2014-2018 are very important to Thailand. They show the potential in production and innovation. They have growth and competitive potential. The Thai economy is a mixed developing economy. Thailand is a newly industrialized country (Kunwatbundit, 2018). When considering the global gross domestic product in 2019, Thailand ranked 22nd with 529,177 million US dollars. The International Monetary Fund (IMF) reported the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) around the world in 2019 that it is the market value of final goods and services produced within the country, regardless of the national resource used to produce the products. The GDP is estimated using the US dollar (Messi, 2020).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Spiritual leadership is important in various organizations. It is effective leadership. Therefore, it is like a leader in managing excellence in the 21st century (Rezach, 2002). Truly adding value to an organization must be developed by using spiritual leadership (Aydin & Ceylan, 2009). Indicators in the recent research form the business world reflect the need for spiritual leadership because it is a response to job satisfaction, recognition of individual differences in organizations, understanding the spirit of the organization and the work of personnel in the organization (Klenke, 2003). Consequently, employees expect and strive for meaningful experiences in life from work and hope that the business organization in which they work will be able to respond to these needs. Employing spiritual leadership is a basic need of both leaders and followers. Spiritual leadership is a leadership style based on developing a person's potential from the inside out. This characteristic of spiritual leadership is very necessary for professionals who are dealing with various types of problems (Somkamlang & Chaiyasit, 2012).

Spiritual leadership has a significant impact on organizational effectiveness because of the use of ethical leadership, compassionate leadership, and Moral Leadership. Using spiritual leadership equips top executives with ethics, values, and spirit (Chen & Yang, 2012; Hackett & Wang, 2012). Spiritual leadership is creating a vision and good organizational culture based on altruistic love, generating a feeling of being accepted. It emphasizes the leader's unconditional care and altruistic love and also considers the growth and development of the individual. On the other hand, the majority consensus among practitioners and academics is that vision is seen as important in guiding and motivating employees (Fry et al., 2017). Vision in spiritual leadership styles gives real meaning and purpose to life and is spiritually grounded (Fry, 2003). A commonly accepted vision motivates and inspires workers to improve performance (Fry et al., 2011) and promotes creativity (Parameshwar, 2005).

The Effect of Spiritual Leadership on Organizational Effectiveness

In the long term, personnel have behavioral changes. The lack of enthusiasm about work and new things causes poor quality work, work late, frequent leave from work, etc. Moreover, organizational executives must analyze and solve problems of negative job satisfaction and attitudes using spiritual leadership to convince subordinates to feel like a part of the organization. The employees, then, have organizational commitment, make progress in work and work with happiness. This is for the survival of everyone in this business. With unstable economic and political conditions, it causes many organizations to have to change their management in order to continue doing business, such as changing organizational structures, reducing the size of the organization, terminating employment, transferring personnel, reducing salary, determining more clear goals for working and a more rigorous performance evaluation method. These are not good for both personnel and the business itself. In order to maximize the organization's benefits, there are an increasing number of studies looking for new methods to measure personnel attitudes and behaviors called organizational commitment, apart from studies on reduction of the turnover rate of personnel. The results of most studies are only to reduce the turnover rate of personnel (Saks, 2006; Pariya & Krishnaveni, 2012; Bakker & Leiter, 2010; Bogaert, Deforche & Martelaer, 2014).

Organizational commitment is used as a predictor of employee retention. It has become a focus of management and human resources departments in many organizations (Kerdpitak, 2022). For example, the primary responsibility of human resources (HR) managers is to understand the factors that create employee commitment and then use that knowledge to improve employee retention and organizational productivity (Steel, Griffeth & Hom, 2002). Organizational commitment refers to the strength of individuals, identification, and participation in a specific organization (Mowday, Steers & Porter, 1979; Porter et al., 1974). It is the emotional commitment of each employee to the organization based on their perception of the organization's goals (Allen & Meyer, 1990; Singh & Gupta, 2015). Finally, the continuum from organizational commitment is the extent to which each employee feels committed to the organization because of its economics (Allen & Meyer, 1990).

Organizational commitment reflects employees' loyalty to the organization and the obligations of each person in that organization (Dolatshah & Hosseini, 2016; Yousef, 2000). High employee commitment to the organization makes the organization highly effective and likely to be motivated to achieve the organization's objectives. Organizational commitment (OC) has three dimensions: affective commitment (AC), normative commitment (NC), and continuance commitment (CC) (Liou, 2008; Allen & Meyer, 1990). Organizational commitment is another factor that affects the organizational performance. If employees are committed to the organization, it results in employees having a desire to work for the organization to the best of their abilities, feeling of wanting to protect and lead the organization to success, and having teamwork. These will drive performance to reach goals (Allen & Meyer, 1990).

Teamwork is an important aspect of work that can be expected to positively affect organizational effectiveness and organizational commitment so that people in the team can cooperate and have the same goal. Team building is important no matter what organization you are in or what work you do. The better the relationship with the team member and the more open to each other, the resulting work will be better. However, the methods for building team relationships will vary from organization to organization. For good teamwork, individuals in a team must work together. Everyone in the team must invest their thoughts and energy for the work or for the success of the work. It is not considered to be the work of only one person, but the entire work belongs to the team.

In addition, a good team should create a working atmosphere where there is trust and commitment to create love and unity in the team. When the team is effective in working, the team and organization will receive benefits. Working will have enormous power and many outcomes will happen. It will help reduce working costs make higher quality work. It can also create new things or innovations for the business, which is the heart of the organization because working as a team will result in organizational effectiveness (Zincirkiran et al., 2015). Teamwork has a significant positive effect on job satisfaction (Musriha, 2013). Over the years organizational commitment and job satisfaction (JS) have received the attention of researchers in different disciplines and have received the attention of many organizations mainly because of their impact on organizational outcomes (McKinnon et al., 2003).

Job Satisfaction depends on many factors within an individual's control. Job satisfaction influences both employees and organization. If employees are not satisfied with their work, it will result in a lower production level, decreased efficiency, higher job stress and high turnover rates (Holland, 2018). Low job satisfaction can also lead to low morale and organizational loyalty. Job satisfaction is related to organizational commitment. Employees who are satisfied with their jobs will affect the organization in a positive way. They help others and do their own work more than the organization expects. Negative job satisfaction and the low-to-moderate relationship associate with high employee absenteeism and turnover (Robbins, 2005; George & Jones, 2008).

Job satisfaction is one of the most researched areas in the social sciences. Employee job satisfaction is highly desirable for any organization that wants to compete in a niche market. Job satisfaction depends on internal factors and control of each organization. Any organization

that has employees with high job satisfaction will have organizational effectiveness more than organizations with employees with low job satisfaction (Robbins, 2009). Job Satisfaction will result in employees working happily. It affects the efficiency and effectiveness of the organization and organizational potential. Organizations that conduct job satisfaction surveys regularly will be able to solve problems more effectively and change things for the better in a timely manner. The most important factors that affect employee job satisfaction are progress in work and salary rate. Human resources management is considered an important factor that makes a business successful and achieves its goals (Robbins, 2009; Bakoti, 2016).

Organizational effectiveness is the long-term ability of a company to achieve its strategy and continue to operate with goals (Cameron & Whetton, 1981). It is the extent to which an organization achieves its goals due to multidimensional variables (Cameron, 1986). Organizations are judged on their effectiveness by setting criteria for measuring effectiveness. Organizational effectiveness is defined as the ability of the organization to mobilize energy for production and adaptation. Effective organizations tend to produce better quality products and are resilient in the face of problems and adversities in order to effectively operate the organization according to its goals. Teamwork can also lead to organizational effectiveness (Christian, Slaughter & Garza, 2011; Saks, 2006).

METHODOLOGY

The study was a mixed methods research. The population was personnel working in the top 100 businesses with the highest incomes in Thailand during the fiscal year 2014-2018 (5 sequential years) in 44 places (Department of Business Development, 2019). For quantitative research, the sample size was calculated according to the criteria of 15-30% of places, so the businesses in 20 places from 44 places was selected (100 x 20%) (Srisa-at, 1992). The sample of 320 personnel was arisen from the concept of at least 20 times greater than the numbers of the empirical variables (16 empirical variables x 20), as suggested by Hair et al. (2010). Systematic sampling from 20 businesses, 16 persons each, was used. For qualitative research, in-depth interviews with 17 key informants were divided into 2 groups: 14 personnel working in the top 100 businesses with the highest incomes in Thailand, 1 person from each location, and 3 academics or experts.

RESULTS

The normal distribution of the 16 observed variables studied in the structural equation model was examined, using the chi-square test (χ^2). If it was found to be statistically significant at the .05 level, it means that such variables were non-normally distributed. On the other hand, if it was found to be not statistically significant (P-value > .50), it means that such variables were normally distributed.

Table 1: Mean (M), Standard Deviation (SD), percent coefficient of variation (%CV), skewness (Sk), kurtosis (Ku) and P-value of the chi-square test (χ^2) of the empirical variables (n=320)

Variable	\bar{X}	S.D.	%CV	Sk	Ku	χ^2	P-value
Vision	3.89	0.75	19.28	-1.146	-.076	1.320	.517
Hope	3.82	0.63	16.49	-1.343	1.919	5.487	.064
Altrui	3.61	0.73	20.22	-.753	.419	.743	.690
Trust	3.62	0.72	19.89	-.637	.386	.555	.758
Affec	4.11	0.69	16.79	-1.783	-.324	3.285	.194
Conti	4.07	0.74	18.18	-1.923	-.809	4.351	.114
Norm	4.21	0.78	18.53	-3.061	-2.059	13.607	.001
Objec	4.10	0.73	17.80	-2.070	-.752	4.852	.088
Relat	3.90	0.73	18.72	-1.232	-.365	1.652	.438
Accep	3.82	0.82	21.47	-1.349	-.232	1.875	.392
Intri	3.83	0.82	21.41	-1.540	.422	2.550	.279
Extri	3.76	0.85	22.61	-1.300	-.389	1.840	.398
Goal	3.73	0.73	19.57	-1.276	.983	2.594	.273
Produ	3.91	0.67	17.14	-1.126	.844	1.981	.371
Adapt	3.96	0.65	16.41	-1.137	1.180	2.683	.261
Innov	3.97	0.64	16.12	-1.114	1.375	3.132	.209

Note: chi-square (χ^2) with statistical significance (P-value <.05) indicates a non-normal distribution

The construct validity of latent variables was checked using the confirm factor Analysis technique by considering standardized factor loading of greater than 30 to indicate that the empirical variable is a good factor of latent variable. In addition, the reliability of empirical variables was considered from the R^2 . Moreover, construct reliability (ρ_c) of latent variables greater than or equal to .60 and average variable extracted (ρ_v) greater than or equal to .50 were tested (Diamantopoulos and Siguaw, 2000) as follows.

Table 2: Factor Loadings (n = 320)

Variables	Factor Loading (λ)	Error (θ)	t	R^2
1. Spiritual leadership (Spirit)				
1.1 Vision (Vision)	.62	.61	11.11	.39
1.2 Hope and faith (Hope)	.74	.45	13.98	.55
1.3 Altruistic love (Altrui)	.84	.30	16.26	.70
1.4 Trust (Trust)	.76	.42	14.61	.58
2. Organizational commitment (Commit)				
2.1 Affective commitment (Affec)	.80	.36	14.07	.64
2.2 Continuance commitment (Conti)	.87	.24	15.22	.76
2.3 Normative commitment(Norm)	.55	.70	9.66	.30
3. Teamwork (Team)				
3.1 Common objectives and goals (Objec)	.50	.75	8.85	.25
3.2 Relationship (Relat)	.86	.26	15.15	.74
3.3 Acceptance (Accep)	.87	.24	15.39	.76

4. Job satisfaction (Satis)					
	4.1 Internal factors (Intri)	.96	.07	23.38	.93
	4.2 External factors (Extri)	.75	.44	15.37	.56
5. Organizational effectiveness (Effect)					
	5.1 Organizational goal achievement (Goal)	.65	.57	12.28	.43
	5.2 Organizational productivity (Produ)	.82	.32	16.63	.68
	5.3 Organizational adaptation (Adapt)	.81	.34	16.28	.66
	5.4 Organizational innovation (Innov)	.75	.44	14.59	.56
$\rho_c = .85$ $\rho_v = .58$					
hi-Square=2.66, df=2, P-value=0.26410, RMSEA=0.032					

Table 3: Measurement Model (n=320)

Dependent variables	R ²	Effects	Independent variables			
			Organizational commitment (Commit)	Teamwork (Team)	Job satisfaction (Satis)	Spiritual leadership (Spirit)
Organizational commitment (Commit)	.49	DE	-	-	-	.70*(9.08)
		IE	-	-	-	-
		TE	-	-	-	.70*(9.08)
Teamwork (Team)	.80	DE	.43*(8.24)	-	.79*(7.15)	.42*(8.23)
		IE	.41*(3.69)	-	-	.21*(6.31)
		TE	.84*(3.83)	-	.79*(7.15)	.63*(7.50)
Job satisfaction(Satis)	.59	DE	.52*(4.37)	-	-	.31*(3.17)
		IE	-	-	-	.36*(4.25)
		TE	.52*(4.37)	-	-	.67*(10.93)
Organizational effectiveness (Effect)	.69	DE	.61*(3.72)	.44*(8.43)	.47*(8.98)	.33*(3.47)
		IE	.24*(8.60)	-	.39*(8.45)	.38*(4.62)
		TE	.85*(4.59)	.44*(8.43)	.86*(8.16)	.71*(10.52)

$\chi^2 = 120.23$ $df = 75$ $p\text{-value} = .00072$, $\chi^2 / df = 1.60$, $RMSEA = .043$, $RMR = .027$, $SRMR = .043$, $CFI = .99$, $GFI = .96$, $AGFI = .92$, $CN = 273.73$

*statistical significance at the .05 level

Note: In parentheses, they were the t-value. If the value was not between -1.96 and 1.96, it was statistically significant at the .05 level. DE=Direct Effect, IE=Indirect Effect, TE=Total Effect

Figure 1: Adjusted Model (n=320)

The results showed that the hypothesized model was fit to the empirical data by allowing the variance of the standard error (θ) of 19 pairs of empirical variables to be related (df before adjustment equals 94 and df after adjustment equaled 75). It was found that the adjusted model was fit to the empirical data which was considered from the fit indexes as follows: $\chi^2 = 120.23$ df = 75 p-value = .00072 , $\chi^2 / df = 1.60$, RMSEA = .043, RMR = .027, SRMR = .043, CFI = .99, GFI = .96, AGFI = .92, CN = 273.73.

The results of fit indexes found that $\chi^2 = 120.23$, df = 75, p-value = .00072 did not yet pass the criteria because it was not statistically significant (P-Value > .05). However, χ^2 was sensitive to sample size, so $\chi^2 / df (1.60 < 2.00)$, RMSEA (.043 < .050), SRMR (.043 < .050), CFI (.99 > .90), GFI (.96 > .90), AGFI (.92 > .90) and CN (273.73 > 200.00) was considered. Therefore, it can be concluded that the adjusted structural equation model was fit to the empirical data. The estimation of parameters in such models was therefore acceptable.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the adjusted structural equation model of the effects of spiritual leadership, organizational commitment, teamwork and job satisfaction on organizational effectiveness of the top profitable businesses in Thailand was fit to the empirical data at an acceptable level, considered from the following fit indexes as: $\chi^2 = 120.23$ df = 75 p-value = .00072 , $\chi^2 / df = 1.60$, RMSEA = .043, RMR = .027, SRMR = .043, CFI = .99, GFI = .96, AGFI = .92, CN = 273.73.

The estimation was found in the structural equation model as follows.

- 1) Spiritual leadership (Spirit) has a direct effect on organizational commitment (Commit) with an effect coefficient of .70 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 1, spiritual leadership has an effect on organizational commitment, is accepted.
- 2) Spiritual leadership (Spirit) has a direct effect on organizational effectiveness (Effect) with an effect coefficient of .33 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 2, spiritual Leadership has an effect on organizational effectiveness, is accepted.
- 3) Spiritual leadership (Spirit) has a direct effect on teamwork (Team) with an effect coefficient of .42 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 3, spiritual leadership has an effect on teamwork, is accepted.
- 4) Spiritual leadership (Spirit) has a direct effect on Job satisfaction (Satis) with an effect coefficient of .31 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 4, spiritual leadership has an effect on job satisfaction, is accepted.
- 5) Organizational commitment (Commit) has a direct effect on teamwork (Team) with an effect coefficient of .43 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 5, organizational commitment has an effect on teamwork, is accepted.
- 6) Job satisfaction (Satis) has a direct effect on teamwork (Team) with an effect coefficient of .79 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 6, job satisfaction has an effect on teamwork, is accepted.
- 7) Organizational commitment (Commit) has a direct effect on organizational effectiveness (Effect) with an effect coefficient of .61 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 7, organizational commitment has an effect on organizational effectiveness, is accepted.
- 8) Job satisfaction (Satis) has a direct influence on Organizational effectiveness (Effect) with an effect coefficient of .47 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 8, job satisfaction has an effect on organizational effectiveness, is accepted.
- 9) Teamwork (Team) has a direct effect on organizational effectiveness (Effect) with an effect coefficient of .44 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 9, teamwork has an effect on organizational effectiveness, is accepted.
- 10) Organizational commitment (Commit) has a direct effect on job satisfaction (Satis) with an effect coefficient of .52 and statistical significance at the .05 level. Thus, hypothesis 10, organizational commitment has an effect on job satisfaction, is accepted.
- 11) Organizational commitment (Commit), teamwork (Team), job satisfaction (Satis) and spiritual leadership (Spirit) can jointly predict organizational effectiveness (Effect) by 69 percent.

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